

The role of cure rate on the fracture properties of nano-modified epoxy polymers

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Abstract

The fracture energy of epoxy polymers containing poly-siloxane core shell rubber (CSR) nano-particles were studied. The effect of increasing the cure temperature on the measured fracture energy epoxy resin was investigated. Single edge notched bend tests were performed to evaluate the fracture energy of the bulk polymers. The fracture energy of the unmodified epoxy polymer increased significantly from 339 J/m² to 3,922 J/m² due to the addition of 9 wt.% of CSR nano-particles at a cure temperature of 40°C. Faster rates of curing, which are achieved at higher cure temperatures were found to be detrimental to the as-cured toughness of the modified epoxy polymers. Scanning electron microscopy of the fracture surfaces linked this effect to the loss of a coherent microstructure of CSR particles.

Introduction

Epoxy polymers are used extensively in aerospace, automotive and electronics applications in the form of adhesives, surface coatings and advanced composite materials. The widespread use of epoxy materials in engineering applications is due to the development of toughened epoxy polymers. Soft rubber particles have been the most successful method to enhance the toughness of epoxy polymers [1-4].

The manufacturing processes involved in the formation of toughened epoxy polymers can have a great impact on the material properties and thermal processing can alter the effectiveness of the tougheners. The performance of the final product greatly depends on several phenomena which take place during the curing process: thermal expansion, chemical shrinkage and material degradation or relaxation [5].

From a commercial point of view, minimizing the cure time by increasing the cure temperature and hence the cure rates of the epoxy systems will lead to a reduction in cost. However, when the cure cycle is accelerated to reduce manufacturing time and expense, the possibility of a runaway exotherm is increased which could result in the degradation and breakdown of the epoxy polymer.

The focus of this work has been devoted to the effect of fast cure rates on toughened epoxy polymers which was addressed by systematically varying the cure temperature and hence the cure rate of the studied epoxy systems.

Experimental

Materials

An amine-based cured diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) formed the basis of the different epoxy systems used in the current work. The epoxy resin was a standard DGEBA with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 185 g/eq. The hardener, developed by FAC Technology, is an amine blend tailored to give a glass transition temperature of circa. 80°C and maximum toughness of the resin.

The resin formulation was altered by replacing 10 wt% of the DGEBA resin with a reactive diluent. The diluent agent was a hexanediol diglycidylether (HDDGE) with an EEW of 170 g/eq. The reactive diluent helps the ease of manufacturing by lowering the viscosity of the epoxy resin. The polysiloxane CSR particles were obtained pre-dispersed at 40 wt% in the DGEBA epoxy resin.

Formulations containing 3%, 6% and 9% weight percentage of CSR were prepared and cured isothermally at 40°C, 50°C, 60°C and 70°C. All formulations were post cured at 90°C for 2 hours and cooled to room temperature inside an oven at a low rate of $\approx 1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in order to mitigate against the influence of thermal induced residual stresses.

Mechanical testing and microscopy

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) tests were performed to obtain the fracture energy, G_{Ic} , in the opening mode according to the ASTM standard [6]. The fracture energy was computed using the energy method approach via:

$$G_{Ic} = U/bw\phi \quad (1)$$

where U is the energy under the corrected load-displacement curve, b and w are the thickness and width of the specimen, respectively, and ϕ is an energy calibration factor. A razor blade cooled to -90°C was tapped into the notch prior to testing to ensure the presence of a sharp crack.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to validate the presence of voids and to determine their volume fraction on the fracture surface of SENB samples. Previous studies [7] have shown that if void growth has occurred during fracture, the diameters of the cavitated particles are significantly bigger than the corresponding diameters measured prior to fracture. To investigate further the fracture mechanisms a field-emission gun scanning-electron microscope (FEGSEM) was used to study the morphology of the SENB specimens.

Results and Discussion

Fracture properties

A maximum fracture energy, G_{Ic} , of $339 \pm 77 \text{ J/m}^2$ was measured for the unmodified epoxy polymer. The value was obtained at a cure temperature of 40°C . The addition of CSR nano-particles to the polymer system increased this value significantly to $3920 \pm 140 \text{ J/m}^2$. This represents an increase in fracture energy of approximately 1000 % when the extent of CSR is increased from 0 wt% to 9 wt%.

From Figure 1, it is evident that the toughness of the material increases proportionally to the content of CSR nano-particles added to the epoxy matrix.

Figure 1: Fracture energy versus weight percentage of CSR nano-particles.

The cure rates and cure temperature do not alter the fracture energy and the fracture toughness for epoxy systems containing only a small amount of CSR (0 wt% and 3 wt%).

On the contrary from Figure 2, it is clear that when the amount of rubber particles is significant (6 wt% and 9 wt%), the temperature at which the sample is cured reduces the fracture properties of the material significantly.

Figure 2: Fracture energy versus curing temperature for CSR nano-modified epoxy systems.

For example, the fracture energy of an epoxy system modified with 9 wt% of CSR cured at 40°C is $3920 \pm 140 \text{ J/m}^2$. This value drops to $2411 \pm 156 \text{ J/m}^2$ when the same formulation is cured at 70°C leading to a loss of toughness which is almost 40 %.

Curing rate and toughness

The principal toughening mechanisms associated with CSR nano-modified polymers [8, 9] are (a) localized plastic shear-yielding of the epoxy polymer and (b) plastic void growth of the matrix initiated by cavitation of the toughening particles.

Shear-yielding can be defined as a constant volume process that absorbs energy [10]. For epoxy systems modified with CSR, the rubber particles act as stress concentrators where localized shear bands can originate and this facilitates plastic energy dissipation.

Additionally, CSR nano-particles cavitate. The process absorbs little energy in itself, but is paramount to relieve the state of hydrostatic stress ahead of the crack tip by creating a void, which subsequently allows plastic deformation of the epoxy polymer around the void to occur. Plastic void growth can absorb a significant amount of energy and can be observed experimentally using a SEM by comparing the initial size of the included particles with the increased size of the void post fracture.

The fracture surface of nano-modified epoxy systems cured at 40°C can be seen in Figure 3. In each of these micrographs, a well-dispersed microstructure of voids can be clearly observed. As expected when a higher content of CSR is added to the epoxy mixture, a greater density of voids is visible on the fracture surface. The radius of these cavitated particles is larger than the corresponding radius of the nano-particles prior to failure. This phenomenon demonstrates that void growth has occurred and this is well established as one of the main toughening mechanisms in rubber modified epoxy systems.

From Figure 4, it can be seen that curing of this epoxy system at a higher temperature, and hence a faster cure rate, leads to some clustering and agglomeration of the particles. This is clearly evident in Figures 4 (b) and (c) containing 6 wt% and 9 wt% of CSR particles respectively. Only few voids are still identifiable as coherent structures and retain a spherical shape. In those two pictures, it is clear that the fracture surface of epoxy systems with a high content of CSR nano-particles is an incoherent structure where rounded and elongated shapes are surrounded by irregular features which are similar to fractals. The preformed CSR particles are no longer clearly distinguishable on the fracture surface and bear no relationship to the preformed CSR particles added at the beginning of the manufacturing process. On the contrary, when 3 wt% of CSR was added to the epoxy mixture, the voids are still reasonably well dispersed and they manifest on the fracture surface as circular objects.

By comparing the different micro-graphs, it is possible to observe that when the rate of cure of the epoxy resin is increased, the dispersion of the CSR particles is affected. In

the epoxy polymer with high content of CSR, the toughening additives interact with each-other, coalesce and as a result the voids observed on the fracture surface are not evenly distributed.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3: SEM images of the fracture surface of epoxy systems cured at 40°C containing 3 wt% (a), 6 wt% (b), and 9 wt% (c) of CSR nano-particles.

Hence, the toughening effect of the CSR nano-particles is inhibited since the growth of the voids surrounding these particles is limited by their surrounding space at the micro-structure of the material.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3: SEM images of the fracture surface of epoxy systems cured at 70°C containing 3 wt% (a), 6 wt% (b), and 9 wt% (c) of CSR nano-particles.

Figure 2 clearly highlights this conclusion since for epoxy systems containing 6 wt% and 9 wt% of CSR nano-particles, the fracture energy of the material drops significantly as the cure temperature and rate of cure are increased. For epoxy systems containing either no toughening additives or a comparatively small amount (i.e. 3 wt%), the aforementioned trend is not readily apparent in the experimental results since the CSR nano-particles have enough surrounding matrix material to fully grow and form voids.

It is important to note that this is a result of the increase in cure rate and not the increase in cure temperature. In the current work, an increased cure temperature has been used as a proxy for increased cure rate. For an anhydride cured system, e.g. that investigated by Carolan et al. [11], the material was cured at 90°C with a post cure at 160°C. Both of these temperatures exceed the maximum cure temperature in the current work, but the rate of cure in the anhydride cure system will be significantly lower than for the amines investigated in the current work, due to the lower reactivity of the anhydride hardening agent.

Conclusions

The fracture properties of epoxy polymers modified with poly-siloxane core-shell rubber (CSR) nano-particles were studied. The effect of cure temperature and rate of cure was also investigated. Several conclusions can be drawn from the current work.

The addition of CSR nano-particles to the epoxy matrix leads to a significant toughening of the polymer. For CSR nano-modified epoxies, the speed of cure is the decisive factor which determines the effectiveness of the toughening additives.

When fast cure cycles are applied, the weight fraction of CSR nano-particles present in the epoxy system is the principal indicator of the extent to which the increase in toughness of the epoxy polymer is inhibited. The higher the content of CSR particles, the greater the drop-in fracture energy observed experimentally.

On these grounds, when designing the cure cycle of toughened epoxy systems in an industrial or commercial setting, the detrimental effects on the toughness which arise as a result of both high temperature and faster cure cycles should be properly accounted for.

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